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Entrepreneurs' Ascertainment Of Technical Skills Needed By Electrical Installation And Maintenance Work Students In Technical Colleges In Anambra State In An Era Of Economic Uncertainties

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ABSTRACT

The study was necessitated by the need to improve technical skills acquisition of students in electrical installation and maintenance work in technical colleges in Anambra State, as a step towards addressing economic uncertainties in Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study. The study adopted the survey research design. The researchers used a purposive sampling technique to select 35 electrical installation entrepreneurs in Anambra State. Researcher made instrument face validated by three experts in the field of technical education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Umuze were used for data collection. A pilot study was used to establish the reliability of the instrument to 20 entrepreneurs in Imo State who were not part of the population of the study. Internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha technique and reliability coefficient value of 0.73 was obtained. Mean was used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study indicated that the ability to discover various types of HT/LT cables and their application is very highly needed while ability to measure and determine the size of winding wire/strip for primary and secondary sides of the transformer among others are moderately needed by electrical installation and maintenance works students for effective technical skill development. Based on the findings, conclusion was drawn that the awareness of technical education and entrepreneurship education will help stabilize the economy and reduce unemployment drastically and it was recommended among others that the current curriculum for technical colleges be reviewed and updated to include some essential components that are lacking to equip the students adequately for self-reliant.

Keywords: Technical skills acquisition, students, entrepreneurship education

INTRODUCTION

Global economic depression has forced nations to revamp programmes to alleviate poverty, create job opportunities and tackle global crisis for innovation and economic sustainability. In this quest however, Nigeria is not left behind, hence the synergy of entrepreneurship education and Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programmes. Entrepreneurship education is the type of education given to a person to acquire the competencies necessary to explore and exploit opportunities into viable venture and thereafter establish and manage the venture successfully. Supporting this view, Obi and Obi (2019) affirmed that entrepreneurship is a process of investing one's skills, administrative competence in setting up a small scale or medium scale business venture with the view of creating employment and enhancing sustainable economic development in Nigeria. The need for unemployment reduction, poverty eradication and wealth creation in the society supports the inclusion of Entrepreneurial skills training in Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Programmes in schools in the country. It also calls for making every graduate an entrepreneur, since paid employment is no longer easily to come.

In furtherance to this, technical education on the other hand at all levels of education system emphasizes acquisition of technical skills. Uwaifo, (2010), viewed technical education as education and training which encompasses knowledge, skills, competencies and structural experiences for securing jobs in various sectors of the economy and even enabling an individual to become self-dependent by being a job creator. Uwaifo (2010) further stressed that if technical education is delivered appropriately to facilitate acquisition of technical skills, individuals could explore their environment and harness the resources which could serve them and create wealth for the society.

Looking critically at the potentials of entrepreneurship education and its synergy with TVET programmes in the nation's schools as being canvassed in this study, there is no doubt that Nigeria will certainly witness a strengthened and revolutionized economy. For TVET programmes to be effective and functional, this critical area (electrical installation and maintenance work), students must be equipped with the relevant technical and entrepreneurial skills. Technical skills in electrical installation and maintenance work are those capabilities involved in a task or various tasks that learners are expected to acquire as a result of persistent practice as offered by technical colleges. Also electrical installation and maintenance work comprises three modules namely; domestic and industrial installation, cable jointing and battery charging, and winding of electrical machines. Students offering electrical installation and maintenance work are expected to acquire technical skills in installing, operating, maintaining, and repairing of electrically energized systems such as residential and industrial buildings. It is also expected that they should be able to set up their own businesses, become self-employed and be able to employ others, (Eze, 2019). Unfortunately, it is common knowledge that graduates of technical colleges lack the relevant technical skills that will enable them to be self-reliant. This view is in line with the assertion of Dauda, Diraso, Yaduma, and Agbu (2017) that most students pass- out through colleges without functional technical skills. It is in this awareness that the authors are spurred to identify relevant technical skills needed by technical college students to be successful entrepreneurs and self-employed after graduation.

Statement of Problem

The development of sound technical and vocational education is central to the nation's desire of becoming industrialized and self-reliant (Akamobi, 2019). However, present realities in Nigeria in this economic uncertainty era indicate that it will take more than a mere refocusing of technical education in its present format to make it more relevant, responsive and effective in delivering graduates with requisite technical skills that can perform to the satisfaction of the society. It is common knowledge that something vital is missing from graduates of technical colleges in technical skill area. According to Dauda, Diraso, Yaduma, and Agbu (2017), this could be attributed to gap between the technical skills taught in colleges and the actual technical skills needed in the society. The situation of poor performance in technical skills seen among graduates of technical colleges has forced Nigerian public to question the relevance of the nation's technology education programmes since the skills acquired by its graduate are not giving them jobs or helping to reduce unemployment in the country. The need to collaborate with entrepreneurs in

electrical installation industry to ascertain the technical skills needed by electrical installation and maintenance works students in technical colleges in Anambra State for addressing economic uncertainties for sustainable development in Nigeria becomes imperative.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study is to ascertain the technical skills needed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work students of technical colleges in Anambra State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which technical skills are needed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work students in Cable Jointing.
2. Ascertain the extent to which technical skills are needed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work students in Winding of Electrical Machines.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study in the entrepreneurs' appraisal

1. To what extent are the technical skills needed in cable jointing by electrical installation and maintenance work students in technical colleges in Anambra State?
2. To what extent are the technical skills needed in winding of electrical machines by electrical installation and maintenance work students in technical colleges in Anambra State?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey research design. The study was ideal because the work sought the opinions of entrepreneurs with respect to the technical skills needed in domestic and industrial installation by technical college students in electrical installation and maintenance work. The population comprised 35 entrepreneurs in electrical installation registered with the States Chamber of Commerce and Industries in both rural and urban areas. A purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents for the study. A 33-item questionnaire titled "Entrepreneurs Ascertainment of Technical Skills Needed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students in Technical Colleges was the instrument used to collect data for the study. The items were structured on a four point scale of Very Highly Needed (VHN), Highly Needed (HN), Moderately Needed (MN), and Slightly Not Needed (SNN). Validation of the instrument was carried out by presenting the topic, the purpose, and research questions to three experts, two in technical education from Department of Electrical/Electronic Technology Education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Umuze and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation, School of Education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Umuze. These experts critically examined the instrument for relevance of content and clarity of statements. Their suggestions and corrections guided the researchers in arriving at the final version of the instrument used for the study. Reliability of the instrument was established by administering 20 copies to entrepreneurs in electrical installation in Imo State who were not part of the study. Cronbach Alpha formula was used to determine the instrument's internal consistency. A reliability co-efficient of 0.73 was obtained. Copies of the questionnaire were administered directly to the respondents with the help of research assistants. The completed copies of the questionnaire were collected from the respondents by hand and were used for analysis. The decision rule was that all items with mean score of 3.50 and above were regarded as being very highly needed, 2.50-3.49 as being highly needed, 1.50-2.49 as being moderately needed and 0.50-1.49 as being lowly needed.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analyses of the study were presented in Tables 1 &2.

Research Question One: *To what extent are the technical skills needed in cable jointing by electrical installation and maintenance work students in technical colleges in Anambra State?*

Table I: Mean Ratings of the Extent of Technical Skills needed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students in Cable Jointing.

S/N	Cable Jointing Skills	<u>X</u>	Remark
1.	Ability to read and interpret the blue print reading (electrical layout drawing)	2.50	HN
2.	Ability to carryout insulation, maintenance and repair works of electrical AC/DC	3.26	HN
3.	Ability in using fittings, plumbing and sheet metal tools	3.30	HN
4.	Ability in using electrical instrument like voltmeter, ammeter, wattmeter and energy meter	3.16	HN
5.	Ability to carry out wiring and earthing system	2.50	HN
6.	Ability to discover various types of HT/LT cables and their application	3.55	VHN
7.	Ability to join and terminate different types of cables	3.02	HN
8.	Ability to carry out maintenance test, fault finding and repairing of underground cables	3.34	HN
9.	Ability to perform safety practices to avoid return current when working on cables	3.50	VHN
10.	Ability to know various types of cables and their application.	3.16	HN
11.	Ability to use various components while jointing	1.58	MN
12.	Ability to position two cables to be joined for correct sequence	1.73	MN
13.	Ability to know various types of HT/LT cable joints and their application	3.00	HN
14.	Ability to know different types of tapping like	3.60	VHN
15.	flowering, stress core making and cable core polishing		
16.	Ability to prepare cores, fitting of joint boxes	2.70	HN
17.	Ability to conduct visual inspection	3.01	HN
18.	Ability to conduct test in underground cables and trouble shooting	2: 40	MN
	Mean of Means	2:97	HN

Data in Table 1 show that 12 items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 13, 15, 16 and 18 had mean ratings ranging between 2.50-3.00 which means the technical skills are highly needed. Items 11, 12 and 17 had mean ratings ranging between 1:58 to 2.40 which means the technical skills are moderately needed. Items 6, 18 and 19 had mean ratings ranging between 3.50 -3.63 which means the technical skills are very highly needed. The mean of means of 2.97 shows that entrepreneurs are of the opinion that technical skill are highly needed by electrical installation and maintenance work students in technical colleges in Anambra

State for addressing global crisis and sustainable economic growth, innovation and strengthening of technical education.

Research Question Two: *To what extent are the technical skills needed in winding of electrical machines by electrical installation and maintenance work students in technical colleges in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Mean Ratings of the Extent of Technical Skills Needed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students in Winding of Electrical Machines.

S/N	Skills Needed in Winding of Electrical Machines	X	Remark
1.	Ability to insert and dress the insulation material in each slot of the motor	3.51	VHN
2.	Ability to insert coil and mark start and end point	2.43	MN
3.	Ability to identify machine enclosures	3.51	VHN
4.	Ability to assemble and run the electrical motor without varnishing	2.40	MN
5.	Ability to test continuity and winding insulation	3.63	VHN
6.	Ability to measure and determine the size of winding wire/strip for primary and secondary sides of the transformer	2.40	MN
7.	Ability to test and identify the faults in the primary and secondary sides of the transformer	3.00	HN
8.	Ability to dismantle the core and coil	2.50	HN
9.	Ability to repair and rewind the faulty coils	2.10	HN
10.	Ability to clean the core and provide suitable insulation	2.50	HN
11.	Ability to perform wind using hand/ or motorized coil winding	3.23	HN
12.	Ability to reassemble the coils of primary and secondary sides of the transformer	3.00	HN
13.	Ability to test transformer insulation, transformation ratio and performance	3.54	VHN
	Mean of Mean	2.83	HN

Data in Table 2 shows the mean ratings of entrepreneurs on the extent of technical skills needed in winding of electrical machines. Items 21, 22 and 24 had mean ratings ranging between 2.40-2.43 which means that the technical skills are moderately needed. Items 27, 28, 29, 30, 31 and 32 had mean ratings ranging between 2.50 -3.42 which means that the technical skills are highly needed item 23, 25 and 33 had mean ratings ranging between 3.51-3.63 which means that the technical skill are very highly needed. The mean of means of 2.83 shows that entrepreneurs are of the opinion that the technical skills in winding are highly needed by electrical installation and maintenance work students in technical colleges in Anambra State for addressing global crisis and sustainable economic growth, innovation and strengthening of technical education.

DISCUSSION

The result of analysis of Research Question 1 revealed that technical skills in cable jointing are highly needed by electrical installation and maintenance work students in technical colleges in Anambra State Nigeria. This finding is partly in consonance with the earlier assertion of Uwaifo, (2010) who submitted that for sustainable economic growth and development, learners need technical skills to contribute effectively to the society. Similarly, in another study Obi and Obi, (2019) noted that technical skills in electrical installation are highly needed among technical students to make them employable or self-reliant.

Regarding Research Question 2, the finding indicates that the entrepreneurs accepted that technical skills in winding of electrical machines is highly needed by electrical installation and maintenance work students in technical colleges in Anambra State Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with the earlier submission of Eze, (2019) who asserted that employers are looking for graduates who are highly skilled and productive enough to identify and solve problem in industries.

CONCLUSION

Technical skills in electrical installation and maintenance work are very important and necessary as they are veritable tools in addressing global crisis for sustainable economic growth. The awareness of technical education and entrepreneurship education will help stabilize the economy and reduce unemployment drastically. Again, as job market approaches saturation point the certainty of finding a job upon graduation declines. It is therefore, imperative that technical college students are imparted with technical skills for self-employment through a synergy with entrepreneurship education.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Curriculum for technical colleges be reviewed and updated to include some essential components that are lacking to equip the students adequately for self-reliant.
2. The federal government should establish a council that will oversee to the appropriate skilling of students of technical colleges.
3. Technical college students should be included in supervised industrial work experience scheme (SIWES) programme to ensure that students are exposed to technical skills by establishments.

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